

Real-time monitoring of Graphene Quantum Dots formation during electrosynthesis on *nc*-ITO

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Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: We report preparation of strongly confined Graphene Quantum Dots with chemical composition $C_{60}H_{23}(COOH)$ from oligophenyl precursor chemisorbed on a surface of nanocrystalline ITO (*nc*-ITO). We show that reported method can be used to prepare controlled single layer GQD films on the ITO surface. The method can also be used to monitor the conversion of the precursor into GQD in real time.

1. Introduction

Graphene, a two-dimensional carbon allotrope consisting of an extended sp^2 -bonded honeycomb lattice, has attracted considerable interest because of its exceptional electrical, optical and mechanical properties.¹ However, zero band gap of pristine graphene limits its direct implementation in many semiconductor and optoelectronic applications. One effective strategy for addressing this limitation utilizes reduction of graphene dimensions to the nanoscale, leading to modification of its electronic structure through quantum confinement and edge-state effects. The resulting structures with lateral dimensions smaller than hundred nanometers are commonly described by the term graphene quantum dots (GQDs).^{2,3} Unlike conventional semiconductor quantum dots, GQDs combine nanoscale electronic confinement with high chemical stability, tunable photoluminescence, and good biocompatibility.^{2,4} Strongly confined GQDs, typically characterized by lateral dimensions in the sub-10 nm regime, are particularly interesting subset of GQD structures, as their electronic bandgaps are tunable in the visible and NIR spectral ranges.³ The ability to tune the optical and electronic properties of GQDs in this range opened path to exploration graphene related structures in light-emitting devices, sensing, photocatalysis, energy conversion, and quantum electronics.^{2,3,6}

The known methods for preparation of GQDs are typically divided into “top-down” approaches, based on physical (e.g., ion/electron beam) or chemical (e.g. hydrothermal, acid, base) cutting of exfoliated graphene and “bottom-up” approaches, based on systematic stepwise synthesis from small molecular precursors coupled with oxidative dehydrogenation by Scholl method.³ Electrosynthesis has recently emerged as an attractive alternative for bottom-up preparation of GQDs because its mild conditions combined with potential control over oxidation state, defect density, and surface functionalization through electrochemical parameters.⁸ In one example Zeng et al.¹

described an electrosynthesis of GQDs on the surface of Tin-doped indium oxide (ITO). In the described approach, ITO (working electrode) is immersed into a solution of the oligophenyl precursor of the target GQD. The application of the potential onto the ITO electrode leads to formation of GQDs through a radical/phenonium cation mechanism and their layer-by-layer deposition on the surface of ITO.² One limitation of the described approach is the aggregation of the GQDs within the deposited layers, which can make effective exploitation of the tunability of GQD electronic properties in certain applications challenging. In a related work, Ji et al.³ have shown that a monolayer of GQDs can be synthesized with high level of control on oxide surfaces by exploiting GQD precursors functionalized on a periphery by one or more carboxylic acid groups.³ The chemisorbed precursor were converted to a target GQD in-situ by chemical oxidation with $FeCl_3$ (Scholl reaction).

In this work we explored the possibility to prepare of strongly confined GQDs by electropolymerization of oligophenyl precursor chemisorbed on a surface of nanocrystalline ITO (*nc*-ITO). We show that monolayer (or sub-monolayer) of GQDs can be prepared by this approach without GQD aggregation. In addition, we show that the approach can be used to monitor the conversion of the oligophenyl precursor to GQD in real time by Raman spectroscopy, which provides insights into the mechanism of the GQD formation.

2. Results and discussion

2.1 Methodology. The general synthetic approach used in the present work is summarized in Figure 1. Four key steps are identified: 1) Multistep “bottom-up” synthesis of the -COOH functionalized precursor P1; 2) Chemisorption of P1 onto surface of the the nanocrystalline ITO (*nc*-ITO); 3) Initiation of electrooxidation of the surface adsorbed P1 by application of external potential onto the *nc*-ITO electrode; 4) Termination of the reaction turning off the applied potential and rinsing of the product with neat solvent.

Figure 1. Scheme of the methodology used in the electrosynthesis of GQD₆₀.

In the present work our target GQD was conjugated oligophenyl polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon with chemical composition C₆₀H₂₃COOH, which we label here as GQD₆₀. In preparation of the corresponding precursor (P1) we followed a synthetic procedure described in our earlier work.³ Structurally characterized precursor P1 was subsequently chemisorbed onto the surface of *nc*-ITO from ~0.1 M DCM solution. The resulting *nc*-ITO/P1 film was used as a working electrode in the electrosynthesis step. To initiate electrosynthesis, a positive cyclic voltammetry (CV) step was applied at the working electrode. At sufficiently positive potentials the generation of cation radical (or phenonium) leads to a 2-electron oxidation of the P1 followed by formation of a new C-C bond.² The resultant positively charged product after is neutralized by loss of two protons. After nine oxidation steps the P1 is fully converted into GQD₆₀.

2.2 Cyclic voltammetry. Figure 2a shows an example of a cyclic voltammograms collected during for the *nc*-ITO/P1 film upon potential sweep from 0 to +2.1 V vs. Ag wire collected at 50 mV/s. The voltammogram shows a significant increase of the current at +1.71 V, which we attribute to the initial oxidation of the P1. The current increase observed +1.71 V during the initial sweep gradually decreases in subsequent sweeps. This is attributed to the fact that the product contains highly delocalized π -electrons that lose electrons to the anode slowly compared to the P1.

2.3 Spectro-electrochemistry. The gradual oxidation of the P1 into GQD₆₀ can be also monitored optically, by means of spectro-electrochemistry. In this experiment the absorption spectrum of the *nc*-ITO/P1 film is monitored during the potential sweep. According to literature, fully aromatized nanographene of precursor, i.e. GQD₆₀ has an absorption maximum centered near 387 nm.³ The example results are shown Figure 2b. Our results show a systematic increase in the absorbance near 390 nm during the first 10 CV electrochemical cycles with the scan rate of 50 mV/s. In the spectra, we observe a repeating pattern of increase and decrease in absorbance which corresponds to the forward and backward sweep of one CV cycle. One possible interpretation of this observation is that this is a result of *nc*-ITO itself undergoing oxidation and reduction. However, the

systematic increase in the signal near 390 nm over the first 400 sec provides an evidence of GQD₆₀ formation.

Careful analysis of the dynamics of the optical changes reveals that the baseline increase is faster during the first 400s than at times 400s. We attribute this observation to process of oxidation of the formed GQDs. Specifically, we propose that the GQDs (product) formed during the initial cycles are subject to positive charge doping, which takes place simultaneously with the conversion of the remaining precursor to GQD. This can be seen in the plot shown in the main panel of Figure 2b, where after 400s the growth of the characteristic peak around 387 nm is significantly reduced, while a new peak centered around 650

Figure 2. (a) Cyclic voltammogram recorded for *nc*-ITO/P1 film during during the first 10 cycles with scan rate of 50 mV/s in acetonitrile, 0.1M TBAPF₆. (b) Spectro-electrochemistry. Change in absorbance recorded during the multistep electrosynthesis (0 to 2.1V vs Ag wire, 50mV/s) inset: Time trace of wavelength monitored at 390 nm

nm, attributed to the electrically doped +1 state of the GQD₆₀⁺,³ grows rapidly.

Figure 3. Electro-synthesized NG/nc-ITO films: comparison of absorption spectra of *nc*-ITO/GQD₆₀ film with Scholl reaction. inset: photographs of the synthesized films in comparison with *nc*-ITO/P1 films.

2.3 Product electronic absorption spectra. Figure 3 shows a comparison of the absorption spectra of the *nc*-ITO/GQD₆₀ film prepared by solution Scholl reaction and *nc*-ITO/GQD₆₀ film prepared by electrosynthesis. The results show that the key optical features are similar for both products, with characteristic β and p bands detected in both spectra near 387 and 459 nm.³ This provides indirect evidence that the structures of the two products are similar or identical. The inset of the figure shows the photograph of the *nc*-ITO/P1 before and after the electro-synthesis treatment.

2.4 X-ray diffraction studies. Powder X-ray diffraction studies were performed to gain more information on the nature of the NG formed on the surface of *nc*-ITO. Overlapping of two formed NG owing to a π - π stacking would result in a 2θ around $\sim 25^\circ$ - 26° .¹ However, our results (not shown) show only signals corresponding to the In₂O₃ (Indium oxide). The absence of the P-XRD patterns corresponding to π - π stacking suggests the formation of a surface-assembled monolayer of GQD on the surface of *nc*-ITO separated by distances > 0.38 nm (upper limit (distance) for considering π - π interactions).⁴

2.5 Raman spectroscopy of stepwise electrochemical oxidation. Raman Spectroscopy has been used and found effective in probing a graphitic material with respect to its crystalline size, number of layers, edge type, chemical functionality, and type of defects⁵⁻¹³ when compared to other techniques such as NMR, FTIR, STM, AFM, etc. The most important spectral bands in graphene-related material that one would be interested in would be the disorder-induced D band and the G band. The position and intensity of these bands are often considered effective in quantifying the defect concentration present in the materials.^{14,6-13} Herein we study and monitor the formation of *nc*-ITO/GQD₆₀ via electrosynthesis via Raman spectroscopy. The synthesized GQD has a chemical composition C₆₀H₂₃(COOH) consisting of $6n\pi$ electrons ($n=60$) with 19 conjugated rings. Raman spectra of *nc*-ITO/GQD₆₀ in the spectral range 900 to 3000 cm⁻¹ are shown in Figure S5(a) (405 nm excitation). A D

mode (~ 1349 cm⁻¹) and G-band (~ 1610 cm⁻¹) which are attributed to symmetry breaking at defects and edges (H-Passivated) and the in-plane C-C deformations respectively¹³ can be observed in the synthesized *nc*-ITO/GQD₆₀ film, whereas these peaks are absent in a precursor *nc*-ITO/P1 film. To confirm the quality of the formed film, and the position of the D and G bands we compared these results to *nc*-ITO/GQD₆₀ with the same chemical composition previously prepared via chemical oxidation (Scholl reaction). Interestingly, a shoulder D* signal¹⁵ was observed in the solution synthesized *nc*-ITO/GQD₆₀ arising due to asymmetry arising from carboxylate functionality (~ 1261 cm⁻¹), additionally, the D band is off by 19 cm⁻¹ to lower wave-number when compared to electro-synthesized *nc*-ITO/GQD₆₀. A higher-order 2D mode at 2681 cm⁻¹ is more pronounced in the NG films prepared via electrosynthesis, indicating a more ordered formation of conjugated NG (sp² network) compared to solution-synthesized *nc*-ITO/GQD₆₀.

Ex-situ Raman measurements were performed to monitor the formation of the D and G modes as a function of the applied potential, held near the oxidative potential of the precursor, with 0.1 V increments per potential step. First, the functionalized C60 precursor was measured using a 532 nm excitation laser. Characteristic Raman peaks of the precursor were observed at 998.2 cm⁻¹, attributed to the ring-breathing mode; a broad feature between 1200 and 1350 cm⁻¹, with a sharp peak at 1344.4 cm⁻¹, was assigned to the C-C stretching mode.¹⁶ The peak at 1602.1 cm⁻¹ was attributed to the aromatic C=C stretching mode, while the peak at 3056.0 cm⁻¹ was assigned to the phenyl C-H stretch (Figure 4a).

Following precursor identification, a sequential potential was applied for 15 seconds per step. We observed the emergence of a new Raman profile in the 1000 to 1600 cm⁻¹ region, centered at 1300 cm⁻¹, Figure 4b panel (i)-(iii). This change is attributed to the formation of C-C bonds between phenyl groups, which subsequently lowered the intensity of the precursor's C=C mode upon further increasing the potential to 1.9 V (vs NHE), distinct D- and G-like profiles emerged, resembling those of GQD, alongside weaker features around 2500 cm⁻¹ corresponding to second-order Raman modes. As the potential transitioned from 2.0 V to 2.1 V, the peaks at 1300 and 1600 cm⁻¹ sharpened progressively.

This sharpening indicates an increasing population of fully conjugated frameworks relative to partially conjugated intermediates, or potentially the generation of charged species. Finally, the experiment was concluded after a potential hold at 2.1 V followed by a quench potential of -0.3 V for 100 s. A comparison with a reference NG synthesized via a classic Scholl reaction is shown in Figure 4b, panel (vii). To further understand the mechanism behind the evolution of the D and G bands in Raman, theoretical redox potentials were calculated for the P1, Intermediate 1, and Intermediate 2 as 2.03, 1.93, and 1.86 (vs NHE), respectively. This suggests that as the precursor partially fuses to form Intermediates 1, 3, and so on, the oxidation potentials decrease dramatically. As the combined results

suggest, with incremental oxidative potential held, various fused intermediates can form during ex-situ measurements

Figure 4. Stepwise anodic oxidation of P1 monitored via Raman Spectroscopy. (a) Raman spectra of P1 bound to *nc*-ITO (b) evolution of D and G mode with incremental applied potential of 0.1 V vs NHE; (c) Proposed mechanism of oxidation based on theoretical calculations.

3. Conclusions

The electrochemical synthesis of GQD with well-defined structure consisting of C60 carbon atoms were developed. Utilizing Spectro electrochemistry we captured rapid changes in the optical spectra, specifically during the initial cycles of a 50 mV/s cyclic voltammetry scan. Post synthesis characterization, i.e., UV-Vis, Raman and MALDI confirmed the quality of the sample. Further, X-ray diffraction verified the successful formation of these structures as monolayer on the substrate. Finally, a stepwise anodic oxidation of the precursor near its oxidation potential was monitored via Raman spectroscopy supported by theoretical modelling provided key insights into the mechanism of the GQD formation.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Electrosynthesis Synthesis details of the *nc*-ITO/C60, Characterization (Raman spectroscopy, Powder X-ray Diffraction (P XRD, Mass spectrometry, optical characterization methods, Electrochemistry and Spectro-electrochemistry), Computational methods (oxidation potentials). Results (Raman spectroscopy and Powder XRD) (PDF). The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://>

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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